

Sustain Sahel

Project Title: SustainSAHEL - SYNERGISTIC USE AND PROTECTION OF NATURAL RESOURCES FOR RURAL LIVELIHOODS THROUGH SYSTEMATIC INTEGRATION OF CROPS, SHRUBS AND LIVESTOCK IN THE SAHEL

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Main Authors: Jonas Wanvoeke (AA), Jo Rodgers (AA), Fernando Sousa (FiBL)

Deliverable 8.3 Videos for Farmers (M42)

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Author(s)	Jonas Wanvoeke (Access Agriculture), Jo Rodgers (Access Agriculture), Fernando Sousa (FiBL)
Editor	Harun Cicek (FiBL), Carla Pinho (FiBL Europe)
Approved by	Harun Cicek (FiBL)
REA Project Officer	Alina KOZACENKO

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I. Executive summary

During this reporting period, the focus was on the production of the videos for the project. Four videos are expected to be produced by Access Agriculture in the framework of the project, showcasing the innovations tested and validated by SustainSahel.

From these, one video on 'Mulching with trees and shrubs for a better crop' was completed and translated in 4 local languages. Access Agriculture is working on the translation of the video into the last local language.

The second video 'Managing intestinal nematodes in small ruminants' is on advanced stage, almost completed and will be finalized as soon as we receive feedback from FiBL.

For the remaining two videos, we are still in the first stages. Access agriculture is currently writing the drafts of the scripts.

2.Video production

2.1. Production of new project videos

Video production has 5 main steps: Script – Pre filming – Filming – Initial edit – Final edit.

Four topics were identified to produce new videos: Mulching with trees and shrubs for a better crop - Managing intestinal nematodes in small ruminants - Establishing a nursery of leguminous trees - Intercropping with leguminous trees.

The first video on Mulching is completed as described in section 2.2.1. The second video on Intestinal nematodes is almost completed at final stage.

For the other 2 videos 'Establishing a nursery of leguminous trees' and 'Intercropping with leguminous trees' are on script stages.

2.2.1 Video on 'Mulching with trees and shrubs for a better crop'

For this first video, the production process started in 2023 but due to agricultural season keeping farmers busy, we postponed the process of the production to 2024. At last, the video was completed and uploaded on Access Agriculture website in French, English, Mooré, Mooré, Wolof, Fulani, and Serer (See appendix I). This first video is already [online](#). For SustainSahel project, 5 local languages were identified to reach farmers in Mooré, Wolof, Fulani, Serer and Bambara.

2.2.2 Video on 'Managing intestinal nematodes in small ruminants'

For this video, AA has intensively worked for 8 months with the WP 6 team to develop the script which was finalised and approved. AA sent a team to Senegal for filming and the video was drafted and edited. We had an issue regarding the life cycle animation of intestinal nematodes, and our team is addressing it with colleagues from FiBL who will provide an updated version of the animation clip to include in the video. The draft video was shared with WP8 at FiBL for comments and suggestions. Otherwise, this video is almost completed in French. We are just waiting for final approval to upload it on the website. A screen short of the video is in Appendix 2.

Once approved, the video will be translated in English and in the five local languages as well.

3. Dissemination activities related with the Deliverable

3.1 Upload of the videos on Access Agriculture video platform and viewing data

The videos translated in local languages under Sustain Sahel are freely downloadable from the Access Agriculture video platform. Likewise, related farmer-friendly factsheets and audio files are accessible from the platform after registration at www.accessagriculture.org.

The table 3.1 presents an overview of the viewing data about the 9 videos translated for SustainSahel.

Viewing data across SustainSahel languages including French and English for the period of 14 December 2023 to 31 August 2024				
Video titles	Video downloads	Video online views	Audio downloads	Document/Media downloads
Herbal treatment for diarrhoea	40	421	4	14
Enriching porridge with baobab juice	23	233	2	12
Keeping sheep healthy	46	257	3	11
Mulch for a better soil and crop	54	1405	5	11
SLM11 Farmers & pastoralists	16	166	0	9
Living windbreaks to protect the soil	30	186	1	9
Animals & trees for a better crop	76	387	27	10
SLM08 Parkland agroforestry	12	136	0	5
SLM10 Managed regeneration	28	248	1	8
TOTAL	325	3439	43	89

In total, from 14 December 2023 to 31 August 2024, visitors of the website have downloaded 325 video versions. 3,439 people have viewed the videos online. We also noticed 43 audio files, useful for media, were downloaded and 89 downloads of video factsheets.

4. Appendix I

Mulching video in English: [Mulching with trees and shrubs \(accessagriculture.org\)](https://accessagriculture.org/mulching-with-trees-and-shrubs)

Mulching video in French: [Pailler avec des arbres et des arbustes \(accessagriculture.org\)](https://accessagriculture.org/pailler-avec-des-arbres-et-des-arbustes)

Video

Deliverable 8.3 Videos for Farmers (M42)

Mulching video in Moore: [Yāg-y ne tūsā la ne tuudā ti koodā paong sōmblem paase](https://www.accessagriculture.org/video/yag-y-ne-tusa-la-ne-tuuda-ti-kooda-paong-somblem-paase) ([accessagriculture.org](https://www.accessagriculture.org))

Yāg-y ne tūsā la ne tuudā ti koodā paong sōmblem paase
 Uploaded 1 week ago | 172 Views

Download Available Languages Next video

[Guideline to download videos](#)

Taas la baadgi & baasese vadaa kooɗa siingboongii ne wintooɗi aɗem la a boogɗi siingboongii suukem, ti rinda tar yidol ne bo-wa wai sein be baeme. Ra n ke y & baasese la baɗi & ka ku me bal n yik ye, n na yili tgaɗi wili kel n sek, & tuga klog n tobe. Gineg y vadaa puugi pugɗi semond a t n ta a yi k buɗɗi ra ka ta ye. Maag y mng n Lak vadaa, y sa n wa mngɗ bo bausɗi sɗoɗi bogɗi.

Current language: Moore
Categories: Climate change adaptation Soil fertility management Agroforestry Maize Sorghum & Millets
Produced by: Access Agriculture

Share this video: [f](#) [in](#) [m](#) [+](#)

Mulching video in Fulani: [Waqirde payi leɗɗe walla lekkon ngam sonde ko ɓuri moyyude](https://www.accessagriculture.org/video/waqirde-payi-leddje-walla-lekkon-ngam-sonde-ko-ɓuri-moyyude) ([accessagriculture.org](https://www.accessagriculture.org))

Waqirde payi leɗɗe walla lekkon ngam sonde ko ɓuri moyyude
 Uploaded 19 hours ago | 292 Views

Download Available Languages Next video

[Guideline to download videos](#)

Payi, hono wertugol leɗɗe e lekkon nokku kon ina reena leydi ndii e ceree li maange, te ina ɓuɗɓuɗa leydi ndii, qum ina moyyi e kullon nguurkon heen kon. Cuɓoɗe no taayirtin lekkon kon e leɗɗe qee, mbele ina heddo cate jonde ballitooqe leɗɗe qe e fuɗɗi has moyyi. Mbaɗee payi mon e ngesa mon yontare haɗa jonte qe ko adii aawre. Nguddilee seeɗa payi oo so tawi oɗori ngeawre.

Current language: Pwllh / Fulfude / Pulaar
Categories: Climate change adaptation Soil fertility management Agroforestry Maize Sorghum & Millets
Produced by: Access Agriculture

Deliverable 8.3 Videos for Farmers (M42)

Mulching video in Wolof: [Lal u ñax akk garab aki gancax gi ngir ngóob mu gën \(accessagriculture.org\)](https://accessagriculture.org)

Lal u ñax akk garab aki gancax gi ngir ngóob mu gën

Uploaded 23 hours ago | 293 Views

Download Available Languages

Guideline to download videos

Lal up garab yi akk gancax u diwaan bi di na aar suuf si ferrent u jant bi te di warñi ñanggay u suuf si, mu di lu am ngarñi ci mbindéef yuy dunnid ci bir am. Bu leen gor gancax geek garab yi lu dul ci kareef, ndax moy des car yu doy ngir moy marñeef gi fu min sax bu baax. Teg leen lal up ñax gi seen tool 1 wañu 2 ay bés lu jitu jwu bi. Dayyileen ndank lal up ñax bi su ngeem di dugel jwu bi ci bir pax mi.

Current language: Wolof

Categories: Climate change adaptation Soil fertility management Agroforestry Maize Sorghum & Millets

Produced by: Access Agriculture

Mulching video in Serer: [Muurit lanq ke taxar fo pafid yaam a saxad alaa moyna \(accessagriculture.org\)](https://accessagriculture.org)

Muurit lanq ke taxar fo pafid yaam a saxad alaa moyna

Uploaded 23 hours ago | 294 Views

Download Available Languages

Guideline to download videos

Ɓ naaf akke mo taxar ke fo pafid ke i njegna kaa ngopaa lanq ke no njee? ne too a mbaiiis a sunnaand ale mo lanq ke, kaa jagna o njirñi mo ñawoow ke ndefna leen. Ba nu fiak o njilaa pafid ke fo taxar ke nu ngodaa ndax ta yoo a naaq a leyu boo kusefu-juufe ke a mbaag o sax appax. Letinyo muurir lanq ke no qol le muuri bees fa ndakawidu ndi pes fi takwidu soo nduufas.

Current language: Serer

Categories: Climate change adaptation Soil fertility management Agroforestry Maize Sorghum & Millets

Produced by: Access Agriculture

Deliverable 8.3 Videos for Farmers (M42)

Mulching video in Bambara: [Dugukolo datuguli ni jiriw ni jirimisqnw ye walasa ka s\r\xuman kq](https://accessagriculture.org) (accessagriculture.org)

Dugukolo datuguli ni jiriw ni jirimisqnw ye walasa ka s\r\xuman kq
Uploaded 20 hours ago | 317 Views

Download Available languages

[Guideline to download video](#)

Sigida jiriw ni jirunwa ka katalawo be dugukolo tanga file yelan ma'udu di bi dugukolo furti'ni sa, o min nafan ka boni fapisanaman'niwa ma' mima biq yen Aw kana jiri misin'ni ni jiriw kq ni a kq oggusunon ka, walasa jiri bolo sa'aman ka to ye kuma be, walasa ka to jiriw ka k'ni ka xq Aw ye katalawo kq aw ka furo ka digkun 1 ka so digkun 2 ma' samni zwa ka domi kq

Current language: Bambara
Categories: [Climate change adaptation](#) [Soil fertility management](#) [Agroforestry](#) [Maize](#) [Sorghum & Millets](#)

Produced by: Access Agriculture

5. Appendix II

Screenshot of the draft of the video on 'Managing intestinal nematodes in small ruminants'

